

ratio, η_{40}/η_{85} (308/313), as can be seen from the last two columns of Table 1, demonstrates the reliability of the given results in the light of the Stokes-Einstein relations, namely $D = kT/6\pi\eta r$, the terms involved having the usual significance.

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^{13}C Spectra as a Tool for Configurational Assignment of Oximes

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IN the ^1H nmr spectra, the α -hydrogens *syn* to the hydroxyl got more deshielded than the α -hydrogens *anti* to it¹. On the otherhand, in the ^{13}C nmr spectra, the α -carbons which are *syn* to hydroxyl got more shielded when compared to the *anti* α -carbons². It is obvious that this correlation can be used only when both the isomeric oximes are available and not to those oximes which are characterised by the existence of only one of the isomeric oximes. To arrive at the configuration of the latter case of oximes, we have recently developed a method,³ wherein we compared the chemical shift values of the α -hydrogens of the oximes and those of the corresponding ketones. We successfully used the above method to fix the configurations of several cyclic ketoximes^{1,3-6}. In this paper, we report how the ^{13}C chemical shifts could be used as a tool to arrive at the configuration of the above mentioned type of oximes. This method will be useful when the ^1H nmr is helpless for these type of oximes.

It has been observed, in many cases, that while going from a ketone to oxime, the α -carbon *syn* to the hydroxyl are shielded to the extent of nearly

14.0 ppm while the α -carbons *anti* to the hydroxyl are shielded to the extent of less than 8.0 ppm. For example, considering the methyl ethyl ketone and its oximes, cyclohexanone and its oximes and 4-*t*-butylcyclohexanone and its oximes, it could be seen from Table 1 that the above statement is true. It is now proposed that this general pattern in the ^{13}C spectral studies could be used to assign the configuration of oximes where only one isomer is available.

TABLE 1— ^{13}C CHEMICAL SHIFT DATA OF METHYL ETHYL KETONE, CYCLOHEXANONE, 4-*t*-BUTYL-CYCLOHEXANONE AND THEIR OXIMES

Compd.	Chemical shift values of			
	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3^a \\ \quad \quad \\ 1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \end{array}$	27.50	206.25	35.20	17.00
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HO}-\text{N} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3^b \\ \quad \quad \\ \text{N}-\text{OH} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3^b \end{array}$	13.00	158.70	29.00	11.00
$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3^b \\ \quad \quad \\ \text{N}-\text{OH} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3^b \end{array}$	19.25	159.20	21.25	9.75
	Chemical shift value of α -carbon in			
	ketone	<i>syn</i> oxime	<i>anti</i> oxime	
Cyclohexanone and its oxime	41.90	24.40	32.00	
4- <i>t</i> -Butylcyclohexanone and oxime ^c	41.20	24.40	32.00	

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRefs. 10, 11.

We have employed this technique in some 2-aryl-cyclohexenone oximes (1a-c, Table 2) prepared by us⁷. In these cases, it could be readily seen that C-2 carbon gets shielded to the extent of 4 ppm or less, while the C-6 carbon gets shielded to the extent of 14 ppm, compared to the parent ketone (2) indicating that the C-6 carbon is *syn* to the hydroxyl group. Obviously, the hydroxyl group is *anti* to the C-2 substituent.

The ^{13}C nmr spectra were obtained at 90.56 MHz in a Bruker WM 460 spectrometer for approximately 0.5 M solutions in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard. A pulse angle of 37.5° (5 μs) and a repetition time of 3.72 s were used, collecting 32 K data points in the quadrature detection mode for a spectral width of 22 700 Hz at 20–21°. The multiplicity were identified by the usual methods under off-resonance conditions.

a; R=Phenyl
b; R=4-Methylphenyl
c; R=4-Isopropylphenyl

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TABLE 2—¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFT DATA FOR 2-PHENYL-CYCLOHEX-2-EN-1-ONE (2) AND 2-ARYL-2-CYCLOHEXEN-1-ONE OXIMES (1a-c)

Compd.	Chemical shift in ppm									
	O ₁	O ₂	O ₃	O ₄	O ₅	O ₆	O _{1'}	O _{2',6'}	O _{3',5'}	O _{4'}
2-Phenyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-one (2)	197.8	140.3	147.9	26.9	22.9	39.0	186.5	128.6	127.9	127.5
2-Phenyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-one oxime (1a)	155.9	139.2	135.6	22.6	20.9	25.5	186.9	128.9	127.9	127.0
2-(4-Methylphenyl)-cyclohex-2-en-1-one oxime (1b) ^a	156.1	136.6	135.3	22.6	20.9	25.5	186.3	128.7	128.6	135.3
2-(4-Isopropylphenyl)-cyclohex-2-en-1-one oxime (1c) ^b	155.8	136.6	134.8	22.3	20.7	25.2	186.4	128.6	125.7	147.3

^aAr—CH₃ appears at δ 21.1.^bOther signals present are at δ 23.8 (OH₂) and 33.6 (OH).

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Biflavones from *Thuja javanica* and *Thuja gigantea*

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THE genus *Thuja* (Cupressaceae) consists of several species of evergreen trees and shrubs. Sawada¹ in his studies on the distribution of biflavonoids

reported the presence of hinokiflavone in *Thuja standishii* and *T. occidentalis*. Besides these two, four more species have been analysed for their flavonoidic constituents. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of amentoflavone, I-7-mono-*O*-methylamentoflavone, hinokiflavone, I-7, II-7-di-*O*-methylamentoflavone, I-7, I-4', II-4'-tri-*O*-methylamentoflavone from *Thuja javanica* and *T. gigantea*. The structure of these compounds were confirmed by their spectral data and by comparison with authentic samples.

T. javanica and *T. gigantea* were collected from Government Botanic Gardens, Ooty (India). The dried and crushed leaves of *T. javanica* were extracted with boiling acetone. The combined acetone extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure. The dark green gummy mass so obtained was refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and acetone till the solvent in each case was almost colourless. The ethyl acetate fractions were mixed together and dried under reduced pressure. It was then purified on silica gel column, eluting successively with petroleum ether, benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate (90 : 10, 85 : 15), and ethyl acetate. The last three fractions gave usual flavonoid colour test, which were combined and separated into five components by preparative tlc (benzene-petroleum ether-acetone, 36 : 9 : 5) and labelled as TI to TV in order of increasing R_f values.

TI on methylation and acetylation and comparison with authentic samples² was found to be hexaacetate and hexamethyl ether of amentoflavone. The compound TII on acetylation gave a pentaacetate and confirmed as I-7-*O*-methyl ether of amentoflavone (sequoiaflavone) by comparing its spectral data with those of the authentic specimens. The compound TIII, m.p. 345°, gave a pentaacetate, m.p. 240° and methyl ether, m.p. 260°. It was characterised as hinokiflavone by nmr studies. TIV gave a tetraacetate and a methyl ether, the structure was finally established as I-7, II-7-di-*O*-methyl ether of amentoflavone⁴. TV was